

42 Results.- Several metabolites related to CA treatment could be identified by databases
43 and literature, which are mainly sugars, organic acids and phenolic compounds
44 (bioactive compounds).

45 Conclusions.- Good correlation coefficients were obtained between discriminant
46 metabolites and fruit quality parameters. These results suggest that treated strawberries
47 under CA could be considered as bioactive healthy compounds, suggesting that treated
48 strawberries under CA could be used as raw material for the preparation and
49 formulation of food supplements and nutraceutical products.

50

51 **KEYWORDS:** strawberry, controlled atmospheres, untargeted metabolomic profile,

52 GC-MS, DI-ESI-Qq

53

54 INTRODUCTION

55 Strawberry fruit (*Fragaria x ananassa*), is a rich source of bioactive compounds,
56 such as phenolic acids, flavonoids and anthocyanins among others that have been
57 demonstrated to have beneficial effects on human health (Sun, Chu, Wu & Liu 2002s
58 Phenolic compounds are widely recognized for their pharmacological activities, for this
59 reason phenolic-rich foods are associated with a reduced risk to cardiovascular diseases
60 (CVD) (Zafra-Stone, *et al.*, 2007), inhibition of dw-density lipoproteins (Forbes-
61 Hernández, *et al.*, 2017), anti-inflammatory action (Joseph, Edirisinghe & Burton-
62 Freeman 2014) and anti-carcinogenic activities (Bagchi, *al.*, 2004; Gullett, *et al.*,
63 2010). Thèse results place strawberry fruit among the families of functional foods.
64 Therefore, the general perception that strawberry is good for health has encouraged
65 many researchers to look for their “magic” ingredients that contribute to pathological
66 prevention.

67 For this reason, post-harvest studies of fruits are of great importance to fully
68 understand the changes in their biochemical components during the fruit maturation in
69 the plant, using physical, chemical and physiological analysis (Andrade, Aragão, *et al.*,
70 1995). Once that the bioactive compounds have been identified, and the correlation
71 between them established, it is possible to determine the optimum time of harvest for
72 immediate marketing and/or storage, in the case of the use for industrialized production
73 of extracts.

74 The major challenge of post-harvest technology is that fresh product gets the
75 consumer with a similar quality that than of the harvest time, but in addition with
76 improved organoleptic and nutraceutical properties. Strawberry post-harvest techniques
77 often focus on the use of controlled atmospheres (CA) and modified atmosphere
78 packing (MAP) (Kader 2002). The use of controlled atmosphere storage maintain the
79 vegetable product in lower O₂ and high CO₂ atmosphere, reducing respiration rates and
80 delaying the ripening process.

81 Strawberry are especially tolerant to elevated CO₂ concentration between 10-
82 40% during storage, that causes changes in fermentation metabolites (acetaldehyde,
83 ethyl acetate and ethanol), sugars (Bodelón, *et al.*, 2010), organic acids (Fernández-
84 Trujillo, Nock & Watkins 1999), and phenol content (Gil, Holcroft & Kader 1997).

85 These previously cited postharvest studies are mainly focused on the
86 investigation of physicochemical changes, but failed to characterize the biological
87 response of the fruit against to abiotic stress and to fully understand the action
88 mechanisms triggered by the treatment (Zhang *et al.*, 2011). Therefore, metabolomics
89 (Bowen & Northen 2010) based on the complete characterization of metabolites related
90 to the changes suffered by the fruit after postharvest treatment is a good methodological
91 approach to deep insight into the metabolic evolution of product during treatment, as
92 well as its final quality and the production of compounds to be used in nutraceutical
93 formulations and foods supplements. In this way, metabolomics has been used to
94 elucidate metabolic composition of strawberries roots, leaves and fruits, as well as
95 differences in the content of metabolites among species or cultivars and stages of
96 maturity (D'Urso, *et al.*, 2015; Koehler *et al.*, 2015) and optimum growing conditions
97 (Saia, *et al.*, 2015). Since metabolomics is the approach that better characterize the
98 phenotypes of living organisms, it can be a good tool to develop new post-harvest
99 strategies to improve the quality and attributes of strawberry and increase their healthy
100 properties.

101 The aim of this study was to get a global understanding of the metabolomic
102 changes of strawberry fruits in response to different short time storage conditions under
103 controlled atmospheres and low temperatures. For this purpose, a metabolomic
104 procedure based on the use of gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and
105 direct- infusion mass spectrometry equipped with triple quadrupole (QqQ) coupled to a
106 time of flight (TOF) analyser with electrospray ionization source (DI-ESI-QqQ-TOF-

107 MS), followed by statistical analysis based on Partial Least Squares Discriminant
108 Analysis (PLS-DA) was applied to strawberries preserved under different controlled
109 atmospheres to identify bioactive metabolites and to determine the best CO₂ percentage
110 treatment.

111

112 **EXPERIMENTAL**

113 **Material**

114 Methanol and hydrochloric acid were purchased from Fisher Scientific Co
115 (Nepean, Ontario, Canada). Formic acid was supplied by Merck (Darmstadt, Germany).
116 Pyridine and derivatizing agents, namely methoxylamine hydrochloride and N-methyl-
117 N-(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide (MSTFA) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich
118 (St.Louis, MO, USA). Water was purified with a Milli-Q Gradient System (Millipore,
119 Watford, UK).

120 Strawberry plants (*Fragaria xananassa*. cv Fortuna) were harvested in Palos de la
121 Frontera (Huelva, Spain) belonging to the enterprise Fresón de Palos (Santa María de la
122 Rábida Cooperative) and were stored at 0°C during 1 day for minimising its
123 physiological deterioration. A previously assay of cold-storage for 24, 48 and 72 hours
124 at 0°C was performed, being the best results which 48 hours at 0°C (data not show).
125 Twelve plastic boxes containing approximately 0.5 kg of strawberries were placed in
126 each controlled atmosphere container for 48 hours at 0°C and exposed to a continuous
127 flow of air (control samples) or gas mixture containing 10% CO₂ + 5 % O₂ + 85 % N₂
128 (Treatment 1, T1); 20 % CO₂ + 5 % O₂ + 75 % N₂ (Treatment 2, T2) and 30 % CO₂ + 5
129 % O₂ + 65 % N₂ (Treatment 3, T3. Strawberries from each treatment were taken for
130 metabolic analysis, frozen in liquid nitrogen and then stored at -80°C to further analysis.

131

132 **Quality parameters**

133 The quality parameters evaluated for sensory analysis have been appearance and
134 flavour using different numerical scales. The analysis of appearance consists in a visual
135 exam of the strawberries. For this, a scale from 0-5 was used, considering the degree of
136 dehydration (tissue damage) and presence of mould, rot and bruises. The measure of
137 strawberry flavour was carried out by tasting several pieces of fruit. The scale used

138 varies with the intensity in flavour, with 5 being the maximum intensity and 0 if it lacks
139 flavour.

140 **Total soluble solids (TSS)**

141 The content of soluble solids was measured on strawberry juice using a digital
142 refractometer (Milwaukee MA871 Refractometer) and reported as °Brix.

143

144 **Metabolites extraction**

145 Strawberry samples were differently prepared depending on the metabolomic
146 technique applied. All the strawberries samples were previously cryohomogenized
147 using a cryogenic homogenizer SPEX Sample Prep (Freezer/Mills 6770).

148 For GC-MS, the extraction procedure was carried out according to the method
149 proposed by González-Dominguez, *et al.*, (2015). For this purpose, strawberries were
150 cryohomogenized and 30 mg of strawberry samples were mixed with 300 pL of
151 precooled methanol. The mixture was homogenized using a pellet mixer during 2 min
152 and then centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 10 min at 4°C. An aliquot of the supernatant (50
153 pL) was mixed with 30 pL of ribitol (used as internal standard, 0.2 mg mL⁻¹ in water)
154 and dried using a SpeedVac device. Chemical derivatization before GC-MS analysis
155 was carried out using the two-step methodology proposed by Begley *et al.* (Begley, *et*
156 *al.*, 2009). The polar extracts were re-dissolved in 50 pL of 20 mg/mL methoxyamine in
157 pyridine and after vortexing, samples were incubated at 80°C for 15 min in a water bath.
158 Samples were further derivatized by the addition of 50 µL of MSTFA (N-methyl-N-
159 (trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide) and incubated at 80°C for 15 min.

160 When apply DI-ESI-QqQ-TOF-MS, the polar metabolites were extracted
161 following the methodology proposed by D'Urso *et al.*, (2015) with brief modifications.
162 For this, 30 mg of sample were extracted with 300pL a solution of
163 methanol:hydrochloric acid (1% (v/v)) for 24h at 4°C and under stirring and darkness.
164 After the extraction, the mixture was centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 10 min at 4°C. The
165 supernatant was filtered through a 0.22 µm PTFE membrane syringe filter, dried using
166 the speedvac concentrator Savant SPD111V (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and finally
167 diluted in 1.5 mL of methanol:formic acid (0.1% (v/v)).

168 **DI-ESI-QqQ-TOF-MS and GC-MS analysis**

169 Chromatographic analysis was performed following the procedure described by
170 Zhang *et al.*, (2011) with few modifications. The polar extract was analyzed in a gas
171 chromatograph (Trace GC ULTRA) coupled to an ion trap mass spectrometer detector
172 ITQ 900 (Thermo Fisher Scientific), using a Factor Four capillary column (30m x 0.25
173 mm i.d., 0.25 μ m VF-5MS, Varian). Helium was used as the carrier gas with the flow
174 rate at 1 mL min⁻¹ and the injector temperature fixed to 280°C. The column temperature
175 was held at 100°C for 2 min; increased to 200°C with a temperature gradient of 5°C/min
176 and then held to this temperature for 3 min and finally increased to 300°C with a
177 gradient of 10°C/min and then, held for 5 min. The significant MS operating parameters
178 were as follows: ionization voltage was 70 eV (Electronic Impact Ionization), and the
179 ion source temperature was set at 200°C. Data were obtained acquiring full-scan spectra
180 in the m/z range of 35-650.

181 The DI-ESI-QqQ-TOF-MS experiments were performed in a QSTAR XL
182 Hybrid system (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA) using an electrospray (ESI)
183 source. Spectra were acquired in negative and positive ion modes, in a range of m/z 80-
184 1100 at a flow rate of 5 μ l/min. The analytical parameters of the QTOF system were
185 optimized to obtain the higher sensitivity with minimal fragmentation of molecular ions
186 using a mixture of standard solution of rutin, ellagic acid, gallic acid, catechin,
187 chlorogenic acid and cyanidine-3-O-glucoside (10 pmol μ l⁻¹ in methanol) in both
188 ionization modes. In positive mode, the ion spray voltage (IS) was set at 5300 V, the
189 source temperature was fixed at 280°C, with a declustering potential (DP) of 150V and a
190 focusing potential (FP) of 210 V. In negative mode, the IS was set at -4500V, the
191 temperature source was fixed at 500°C and the values of DP and FP were -83V and -
192 250V respectively.

193

194 **Data processing**

195 In order to filter the mass spectrometric data obtained from DI-ESI-QqQ-TOF-
196 MS, and to carry out the reduction into a two-dimensional data matrix of spectral peaks
197 and their intensities, the data were exported to MarkerView software (Applied
198 Biosystems). For this purpose, all peaks above the noise level (10 counts, determined
199 empirically from experimental spectra) were selected.

200 The raw data obtained by GC-MS was processed following the typical pipeline
201 described by Katajamaa & Oresic (2007), which usually proceeds through multiple
202 stages, including, filtering, feature detection, alignment and normalization. For this

203 purpose, the freely available XCMS software, included in the R platform ([http://www.r-](http://www.r-project.org)
204 [project.org](http://www.r-project.org)) was used. GC-MS files were converted into net CDF using the Thermo File
205 Converter tool (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and subsequently, data were extracted using
206 the matched filter method. This algorithm slices data into extracted ion chromatograms
207 (XIC) on a fixed step size, and then each slice filtered with matched filtration using a
208 second-derivative Gaussian as the model peak shape. The XCMS parameters were
209 optimized according to the characteristics of datasets obtained in order to extract the
210 maximum information as possible. Finally, the settings applied for GC-MS data were
211 S/N threshold 2, full width at half-maximum (fwhm) 3, and width of the m/z range 0.1
212 (step parameter). After peak extraction, grouping and retention time correction of peaks
213 (alignment) was accomplished in three iterative cycles with descending bandwidth (bw)
214 from 5 to 1 s. Then, imputation of missing values was performed by returning to the raw
215 spectral data and integrating the areas of the missing peaks which are below the applied
216 signal-to-noise ratio threshold, using the fill Peaks algorithm. For data normalization,
217 the locally weighted scatter plot smoothing (LOESS) normalization method was used,
218 which adjusts the local median of log fold changes of peak intensities between samples
219 in the data set to be approximately zero across the whole peak intensity range. Finally,
220 the pre-processed data were exported as a .csv file for further analysis to eliminate non-
221 significant features following multivariate pr

222

223 **Statistical analysis**

224 The data collected of quality parameters and TSS content were treated using
225 MiniTab 6 statistical software to provide ANOVA significance of each treatment
226 effects. Significant differences between the means were determined using the Tukey's
227 test at $p < 0.05$.

228 For the analysis and visualization of multivariate statistical methods statistical
229 software SIMCA-P (version 11.5, Umetrics AB, Umea, Sweden) was used. Principal
230 component analysis (PCA) for an unsupervised analysis and partial least squares-
231 discriminant analysis (PLS-DA) were performed in order to discriminate between the
232 groups of study. All data were submitted to Pareto scaling to reduce the relative
233 importance values, and logarithmic transformation in order to approximate to a normal
234 distribution. The values of R² and Q² provided by the software, which are indicative of
235 class separation and predictive power of the model respectively, were assessed. Finally,
236 metabolites responsible for discrimination of treatments were selected according to the

237 Variable Importance on the Projection (VIP), considering only variables with VIP
238 values higher than 1.5 as indicative of significant differences among groups. The
239 specificity and sensitivity of the altered metabolites were evaluated according to the
240 area under the curve (AUC value) of the receiver operator characteristic (ROC) using
241 MetaboAnalyst 4.0 software (<http://www.metaboanalyst.ca/>). Also, a correlation
242 analysis by Pearson's correlation coefficient (r ,) were calculated within the discriminant
243 metabolites and the quality parameters (appearance, flavour, and TSS content) using
244 MiniTab 16 statistical software. The level of moderate significance was set as $r \geq 0.6$ for
245 all correlation analysis.

246

247 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

248 **Quality parameters and TSS content**

249 The results of appearance, flavour and TSS that determine strawberry fruit quality are
250 summarized in Table 1. The appearance of strawberries decreases over the shelf-life as a
251 result of the onset of bruises and rot. Treatments of strawberries with CA maintain
252 better appearance respect to untreated ones, being those treated with 20 % of C₂
253 during 48h at 0°C the one which have better appearance after 7 days of shelf-life
254 ($p=0,000$). Statistical analysis of strawberry flavour shows large differences depending
255 of treatments. In this way, the treatment with 20 % of CO₂ during 48h at 0°C produces
256 more intense strawberry flavour. The soluble solids content presented large differences
257 between treated and control samples. The strawberries had an initial value of 8.97 °Brix
258 (at 0 days of shelf-life). After 3 days of shelf-life the value of °Brix of control
259 strawberries decreased to 8.16 while those treated with 10 % CO₂ remained constant.
260 Similarly, strawberries treated with 20 % of CO₂ during 48h at 0°C reached 9.36 °Brix
261 and those treated with 30 % of CO₂ during 48h at 0°C exceed 8.16 °Brix. The TSS
262 decreased with the time in both air and CO₂ treatment and in contrast to the published
263 experiences by other authors (Gil *et al.*, 1997; Pelayo-Zaldivar *et al.*, 2007) exist a
264 difference between treatments ($p=0.001$), being strawberries treated with 20 % CO₂
265 during 48h at 0°C those with a higher value °Brix along shelf-life.

266

267 **Metabolite analysis**

268 In order to investigate metabolic differences an untargeted metabolomic analysis
269 of strawberries based on both GC-MS and DI-ESI-QqQ-TOF-MS was performed to the

270 three CA treatments considered and control samples. The multivariate statistical
271 analysis by PLS-DA allowed a good classification of different sample groups (control,
272 and treatment under atmosphere of 10 %, 20 % and 30 % CO₂ and maintaining always a
273 concentration of 5% O₂ during 48h at 0°C). As it can be observed in Figure 1a, 2a, and
274 3a, that clustering between treatment experiments was satisfactory in all cases getting a
275 good classification among them. This cluster analysis was applied to a total of 32
276 samples, 8 control samples, and 8 samples under each atmosphere as previously
277 described. Furthermore, in order to access the reliability of the methodology in terms of
278 stability and repeatability, quality control (QCs) samples analysed throughout the
279 sequence run were predicted in the model. QCs samples were also good clustered,
280 which indicate results stability during analysis without significant outliers.

281 Thereby, QCs were closely clustered (QCs are prepared by pooling equal
282 volumes of each type of samples), showing a low analytical variability among different
283 runs in which also shows a good classification between treated and control samples. The
284 most significant differences on appearance, flavor and TSS content were observed in
285 samples treated with 20% of CO₂ enriched atmosphere during 48h at 0°C., and for this
286 reason, a second model was developed with data from samples treated under these
287 conditions along with controls to understand the interclass separation and identify
288 potential characteristic markers related to this treatment (Figure 1b, 2b, 3b). The quality
289 of the model was evaluated by the relevant performance statistic of R^2 and Q^2 . In all
290 cases, satisfactory values for the quality parameters were obtained suggesting that all
291 models were valid and highly predictive. The R^2 and Q^2 values obtained from second
292 model were 1 and 0.857 for GC-MS analysis; 0.963 and 0.802 for ESI(+)-QqQ-TOF-
293 MS analysis and finally, 0.987 and 0.908 for ESI(-)-QqQ-TOF-MS analysis.

294 The variables with more influence in the model were selected on the basis of
295 Variable Influence on the Projection (VIP) parameter, only variables with VIP values
296 higher than 1.5 were selected and used to identify metabolites that contribute to the
297 separation between treated strawberries and control samples.

298

299 **GC-MS profile**

300 A total of 29 components were identified in the chromatogram (Figure 2) of
301 polar extracts using the NIST Mass Spectral Library (version 08), considering only
302 those variables with a Similarity Index (SI) greater than 70%. In addition, tandem mass
303 spectrometry was performed for the unequivocal identification of these compounds. The

304 most significant metabolites altered in strawberries treated with 20% of COM during 48h
305 at 0°C respect to the control samples, including sugars (glucose, ribose, inositol) and
306 organic acids (malic acid, oxalic acid, acetic acid, phosphoric acid) among others (Table
307 2).

308 In order to identify the metabolic pathways perturbed by postharvest treatments,
309 MetaboAnalyst 4.0 database was used, which reveals the perturbation of starch and
310 sucrose, inositol - phosphate, pentose - phosphate, pyruvate and glycolysis pathways as
311 well as the TCA cycle. The most altered metabolic pathways in strawberries treated
312 with 20%CO₂ during 48h at 0°C are showed in Figure 3.

313 It can be observed over-expressed levels of inositol (fold change 33.96) and
314 glucose (fold change 6.05) in strawberries under 20% CO₂ enriched atmosphere for 2
315 days at 0°C, but not in fructose and sucrose as observed by Sun *et al.*, (2012) and Wang
316 & Bunce (2004). These metabolites are involved in the glycolysis and inositol
317 phosphate metabolism. The conversion of glucose into pyruvate produces several
318 important precursor metabolites, as 3-phosphoglycerate which connect with the inositol
319 phosphate metabolism. Inositol and their derivatives are sugar alcohols present in fresh
320 strawberry juices having positive physiological effects on humans (Sanz, Villamiel &
321 Martinez-Castro 2004). In plants, inositol is converted by oxidative cleavage to
322 glucuronic acid, which is transformed to pectin and hemicellulose, both cell wall
323 polysaccharides (Loewus & Murthy 2000), and after the storage of strawberries under
324 CA with the conditions above described, undergo down-regulation (fold change 0.15).
325 Inositol compounds are involved in phosphate storage, cell wall biosynthesis, salinity
326 stress tolerance, cell-to-cell communication, storage and transport of plant hormones. It
327 is known that myo-inositol and myo-inositol-1-phosphate among others decrease in
328 over ripening stage of the strawberry (Zhang *et al.*, 2011) which can be retarded after
329 treatments under CA due to its delaying ripening and senescence action. Another sugar,
330 in this case down-regulated by storage under CA and low temperature treatment is
331 ribose (fold change 0.25), which is involved in the metabolism of sugars through the
332 pentose phosphate pathway.

333 The two main organic acids in strawberry, citric and malic acids are important
334 products of TCA cycle. Storage under 20% C₂ at 0°C over-express the last one (fold
335 change 3.63), however, citric acid content was not affected by CO₂ treatment. These
336 results differ from those reported by other authors (Fernández-Trujillo, Nock & Watkins
337 1999; Pelayo-Zaldivar *et al.*, 2007; Ponce-Valadez & Watkins 2008) which report the

338 decrease of both organic acids after postharvest treatments with controlled atmospheres.
339 Nevertheless, Koyunku & Dilmacunal (2010), found an increase of malic acid in 'Dorit'
340 strawberry variety stored at 0°C for 2 days, decreasing with storage during 10 days.
341 Other organic acids present in very small amounts are tartaric, fumaric and oxalic acid
342 (Sturm, Koron & Stampar 2003). Oxalic acid content in 'Dorit' and 'Selva' strawberries
343 decreased after the first 2 days of storage at 0°C as was reported by Koyunku &
344 Dilmacunal (2010) but in the present study, applying 20% C₂ enriched atmospheres
345 and cold storage at 0°C, the content of malic and oxalic acids increased (fold change
346 1.16), decreasing acetic (fold change 0.61) and phosphoric acids (fold change 0.41).
347 Therefore, the results of the metabolomic analysis show an increase of sugars (inositol,
348 glucose) and organic acids (malic acid, oxalic acid) in strawberries treated with 20% of
349 C₂ at 0°C. These results are in good agreement with the values of Total Soluble Solids
350 (TSS) content of the strawberries treated, which have a higher °Brix value in
351 comparison to fresh product.

352 DI-ESI-QqQ-TOF-MS analysis

353 Extracts from treated and control strawberries were analyzed by direct infusion
354 electrospray ionization mass spectrometry in positive ion mode (Fig. 4A) and negative
355 ion mode (Fig.4B) to obtain a fingerprint of the different samples. Identification of
356 compounds was performed by MS/MS, selecting precursor ions according to variables
357 (m/z) with VIP values higher than 1.5 as indicative of significant differences among
358 groups and scientific literature. Table 3 report the identified metabolites altered in
359 strawberries treated with the mixture of 20% C₂ + 5% O₂ for 2 days at 0°C. As shown
360 in Table 3 the compounds identified using this technique are phenolic compounds
361 belonging to flavonols class (compounds 9, 10, II, 12, 13), flavanols (3, 7)
362 anthocyanins (6, 8) and derivatives of phenolic acids and others (1, 2, 4, and 5).

363 Flavonoids are secondary metabolic compounds responsible of colour and aroma
364 in plants that play numerous biological functions such as UV-filter, detoxify agents,
365 defence against pathogen infection among others (Falcone-Ferreira, Rius & Casati
366 2012). Flavonol glycosides are the most numerous group of phenolic compounds
367 identified in strawberries treated with 20% CO₂ + 5% O₂ in this study, including quercetin
368 3-O-glucuronide, dihydromyricetin-hexose, kaempferol-3-O-rutinoside, isorhamnetin 3-
369 O-rhamnoside-rhamnoside-glucoside, and quercetin 3-O-(6-O-feruloylglucoside)-
370 glucoside-7-O-rhamnoside, which have been previously identified in berry fruits

371 (Kárlund *et al.*, 2015; Tian *et al.*, 2017; Spínola, Pinto & Castilho 2015; D'Urso *e/ al.*,
372 2016). Quercetin 3-O-glucuronide, which has been described as the main flavonol in
373 strawberries (Seeram *et al.*, 2006) is down-regulated (fold change 0.741) against other
374 flavonols glycosides which undergo over-expression (peaks no. 10, 11, 12, 13, in Table
375 3). Kafkaletou *et al.* (2017) observed an increase in the total phenolic compounds after
376 the storage under CA in goji berries under similar conditions (5 %O₂, 15%CO₂ at 1°C
377 for 2 days). Others authors such as Selcuk *et al.* (2015) and González-Gómez *et al.*
378 (2017) have experienced an increase in the total flavonoid content in cherries and
379 medlar fruit respectively after long-term treatments with CA.

380 Epi(catechin) hexoside and epi(gallocatechine) were identified by their typical
381 DI-MS and MS-MS data, which are described in previous studies (González-Gómez *et*
382 *al.*, 2017; Del Bubba, *et al.*, 2012). In the present work, both compounds are over-
383 expressed displaying fold change values of 2.831 and 2.604, respectively.

384 Like as flavonoids, phenolic acids are secondary metabolites crucial for plant
385 growth and reproduction (Vrhovsek, *et al.*, 2012) and whose production can be affected
386 by the environment or post-harvest process (Carbone & Mencarelli, 2015; Mozetic,
387 Simié & Trebse 2006). Derivates from phenolic acids such as, caffeoylthreonate (peak
388 no. 1) and caffeic acid hexoside (peak no. 4) are disturbed in strawberry fruit after the
389 storage under 20%CO₂+5%O₂ atmosphere at 0°C for 2 days. Unlike caffeoylthreonate
390 (fold change 1.814), caffeic acid hexoside is down-regulated (fold change 0.688). A
391 characteristic fragment ion at m/z 189, 190 and 171 correspond to cinnamic acid-3-O-
392 acetyl hexoside (compound No. 5) which suffer an over-expression (fold change 2.185)
393 in stored strawberries. This compound has being detected and identified previously in
394 strawberry fruits by Spinola *et al.*, (2015). In addition, 4-(2-Hydroxyethyl)phenol-
395 hexoside (peak no. 2) is a phenolic compound present in others berries like currants and
396 chokeberries (Tian *et al.*, 2017) which undergo to an over-expression (fold change
397 1.203).

398 The main compounds responsible for strawberry colour are anthocyanins,
399 carotenoids and chlorophylls. The main anthocyanins found in strawberry are
400 pelargonidin-3-glucoside and cyanidin-3-glucoside that correspond to the colours
401 red/orange and orange respectively (Nunes, *et al.*, 2006). Peaks 6 and 8 were identified
402 as cyanidin-3-glucoside/cyanidin-3-galactoside and pelargonidin-3-O-acetyl hexoside

403 on the basis of the spectral data and literature and are commonly found in strawberries.
404 The use of DI-MS in positive ion mode do not allow the distinction between cyanidin-3-
405 glucoside or cyanidin-3-galactoside, in this case, it's necessary the use of a
406 complementary chromatographic technique for a better identification. During the
407 maturation of the fruit, the content of the anthocyanins increases (Jimenez, Zambrano &
408 Aguilar 2004; Crecente-Campo, Nunes-Damaceno & Romero-Rodriguez 2012) though,
409 the amount of these pigments varies depending on the variety, crop and can be affected
410 after post-harvest treatments. Accumulation of anthocyanins in similar CO₂ storage was
411 reduced in the cultivars 'Selva' (Gil, Holcroft & Kader 1997; Holcroft & Kader 1999),
412 Northeast and Earliglow (Shin, *et al.*, 2008). These result are in good agreement with
413 the pelargonidin-3-O-acetyl hexoside content which experiences a down-regulation
414 (fold change 0,7), however, the content of cyanidin-3-glucoside/cyanidin-3-galactoside
415 (fold change 1,891) are over-expressed under the storage condition studied in 'Fortuna'
416 and in grapes, the combination of low- temperatures storage and high COC may provoke
417 an accumulation of anthocyanins (Romero, *et al.*, 2008). The content of cyanidin-3-
418 glucoside in strawberries is very low compared to other anthocyanins. This compound
419 has a special interest because it has numerous beneficial properties in human health.
420 Studies in rodents and cell lines highlight the action of this compound against
421 infections, diabetes, metabolic syndromes and cancer among others (Olivas-Aguirre, *et*
422 *al.*, 2016).

423 A possible increase in the concentration of this anthocyanin and the others
424 phenolic compounds in strawberries treated with CA makes it a fruit with high
425 nutraceutical potential.

426 The analysis of polar extracts using GC-MS and DI-ESI-QqQ-TOF-MS enabled
427 the detection of a great number of compounds of different classes. The heat map based
428 on hierarchical clustering analysis (Fig. 5) summarizes the differential distribution of
429 altered metabolites after a controlled atmosphere treatment.

430 **Correlation analysis between discriminant metabolites and quality parameters**

431 In the polar extract of strawberry fruits, a total of 22 metabolites were identified from
432 untargeted metabolic analysis and were submitted to a correlation analysis against
433 quality parameters. Overall, positive and negative dependencies were observed.
434 Metabolites that showed higher correlation coefficients against appearance parameters

435 were caffeoylthreonate, cinnamic acid-3-o-acetylhexoside,
436 gallicatechine/epigallocatechine, dihydromyricetin-hexose, kaempferol-3-o-rutinoside,
437 cyanidin-3-glucoside/cyanidin-3-galactoside, isorhamnetin 3-o-rhamnoside-
438 rhamnoside-glucoside, quercetin 3-o-(6-o-feruloylglucoside)-glucoside-7-o-rhamnoside
439 and glucose. in the case of flavour, caffeoylthreonate, gallicatechine/epigallocatechine,
440 cinnamic acid-3-o-acetylhexoside, dihydromyricetin-hexose, kaempferol-3-o-rutinoside,
441 cyanidin-3-glucoside/cyanidin-3-galactoside, isorhamnetin 3-o-rhamnoside-
442 rhamnoside-glucoside, quercetin 3-o-(6-o-feruloylglucoside)-glucoside-7-o-rhamnoside,
443 glucose and inositol. Finally, the content of soluble solids was correlated with
444 isorhamnetin 3-o-rhamnoside-rhamnoside-glucoside, cyanidin-3-glucoside/cyanidin-3-
445 galactoside, cinnamic acid-3-o-acetylhexoside and glucose.

446 Our results conclude that the use of metabolomic fingerprinting allows a better
447 understanding of the mechanisms of action and response of 'Fortuna' strawberry
448 cultivar after the application of controlled atmospheres and a good correlation with
449 physical-chemical and sensory analysis. GC-MS and DI-ESI-QqQ-TOF-MS stand out
450 as a suitable and complementary metabolomic tools for the characterization of the
451 metabolome of strawberry fruits. The application of this analytical approach and
452 subsequent multivariate statistics has allowed the classification three different
453 treatments in CA and control samples. Preservation of fruits under 20% of CO₂+5%O₂
454 during 48h at 0°C produces alterations in primary and secondary metabolites including
455 sugars (glucose, ribose, inositol) organic acids (malic acid, oxalic acid, acetic acid,
456 phosphoric acid) and phenolic compounds (flavonols, anthocyanins, phenolic acids).
457 These compounds contribute to the strawberry flavour and are considered as bioactive
458 compounds due to its health benefits in humans. The increase in these bioactive
459 compounds after the CA treatment mentioned above allows producing a fruit enriched
460 in bioactive compounds with significant added value from health point of view, that
461 make it a good candidate for the production and formulation of food supplements and
462 nutraceutical products.

463

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615

616

FIGURES

Fig. 1. Partial least squares discriminant analysis (PLS-DA) including all groups from the polar extract of (A) GC-MS analysis, (B) ESI(+)-QqQ-TOF-MS analysis and (C) ESI(-)-QqQ-TOF-MS analysis. Each replicate is one piece of strawberry. Control samples: black; T1: blue; T2: green; T3: orange; QCs samples: red. Second model comparing control samples (red) and T2 (black) of (D) GC-MS analysis, (E) ESI(+)-QqQ-TOF-MS analysis and (F) ESI(-)-QqQ-TOF-MS analysis.

Fig. 2. GC-MS chromatogram of strawberry polar extract.

Fig. 3. Changes of metabolites after CA treatment shown in a metabolic diagram.

Fig. 4. DI-ESI-QqQ-TOF-MS Full scan (50-1100 m/z) of strawberry polar extract in (A) positive ionization mode and (B) negative ionization mode.

Fig. 5. Heatmap based on hierarchical clustering analysis of discriminant metabolites.

TABLES

Days	Appearance					Flavour					TSS				
	Control	T1	T2	T3	<i>P</i> value	Control	T1	T2	T3	<i>P</i> value	Control	T1	T2	T3	<i>P</i> value
0	5					5					8.97				
3	4.75b	5a	5a	5a	0.03	4.5c	4.75ab	4.95a	4.25b	0.002	8.16b	8.96ab	9.36a	8.16b	0.009
5	4.5b	4.75a	4.75a	4.75a	0.000	4b	4b	4.5a	3.5c	0.002	7.10c	7.92b	8.28a	7.82b	0.000
7	4.5b	4c	4.75a	4.5b	0.000	4b	4.25b	4.5a	3.5c	0.01	7.68bc	7.50c	7.94a	7.72bc	0.000

Table 1. Effects of CA on appearance, flavour and soluble solids content (TSS) of strawberry from the first harvest (control, 0 days) and after CA treatment at 3, 5 and 7 days. Appearance are means of all the strawberries content in the plastic boxes. Flavour data are means of 3 individual fruit replicates. °Brix data are means of 5 individual fruit replicates. Values with the same letters do not differ statistically.

Metabolite	Fold Change	Sense of change	AUC value
Glucuronic acid	0.15	}	0.70
Oxalic acid	1.16	↑	0.70
Phosphoric acid	0.41	↓	0.86
Malic acid	3.63	↑	0.77
Glucose	6.05	}	0.94
Inositol	33.96	}	0.77
Acetic acid	0.61	}	0.72
o-D-glucopyranoside	0.13	}	0.94
Ribose	0.25	}	0.78

Table 2. Discriminant metabolites identified by GC-MS profiling for differentiation of strawberry fruits treated under T2 conditions.

No.	Ionization Mode	m/z	MSMS	Tentative Metabolite	Class	Fold Change	Sense Of Change	Literature	AUC value
1		297	135, 89	Caffeoylthreonate	Phenolic acid derivatives	1,814	}	Karlund et al. (2016)	0.91
2	+	301	139	4-(2-Hydroxyethyl)phenol-hexoside	Other phenolic compounds	1,203	↑	Tian et al. (2017)	0.65
3		305	203, 123	Gallocatechin / Epigallocatechine	Flavan-3-ols	2,604	↑	Vrhovsek et al. (2012)	0.92
4	+	343	179	Caffeic acid hexoside	Phenolic acid derivatives	0,688		Tian et al. (2017)	0.75
5		351	189, 190, 171	Cinnamic acid-3-O-acetylhexoside	Phenolic acid derivatives	2,185		Spinola et al. (2015)	0.85
6	+	449	287	Cyanidin-3-glucoside / Cyanidin-3-galactoside	Anthocyanins	1,891	}	Del Bubba et al. (2012);	0.92
7		451	245, 125, 109	Epi(catechin) hexoside	Flavanol glycoside	2,831	}	Del Bubba et al. (2012)	
8	+	475	271	Pelargonidin-3-O- acetyl hexoside	Anthocyanins	0,7		La Barbera et al. (2017); Spinola et al. (2015)	0.76
9		477	301	Quercetin 3-O-glucuronide	Flavanol glycoside	0,741		D'Urso et al. (2016); Tian et al.(2017); Karlund et al. (2016)	0.92
10		481	463, 319, 301	Dihydromyricetin-hexose	Flavanol glycoside	1,807	↑	D'Urso et al. (2016)	0.89
11		593	449, 285	Kaempferol-3-O-rutinoside	Flavanol glycoside	1,940	↑	Tian et al. (2017);	0.99
12	-	771	625, 479, 317	Isorhamnetin 3-O-rhamnoside-rhamnoside-glucoside	Flavanol glycosides	1,745	↑	Spinola et al. (2015)	
13	+	949	303	Quercetin 3-O-(6-O-feruloylglucoside)-glucoside-7-(i-rhamnoside)	Flavanol glycosides	1,956		Tian et al. (2017)	0.97
								Tian et al. (2017)	0.96

Table 3. Discriminant metabolites identified by DI-ESI-QqQ-TOF-MS in strawberry fruits treated under T2 conditions.

Figure 2

299x148 mm (95 x 95 DPI)

Figure 3

600x548 mm (96 x 96 DPI)

222x1 92mm (72 x 72 DPI)